

Power factor correction AC-DC boost converter using PI-hysteresis current control

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ABSTRACT

The AC line input voltage is frequently rectified by single-phase diode rectifiers and filtered using sizable electrolytic capacitors. The capacitor draws current in brief pulses, so harmonics distort the line current, resulting in high losses. Harmonics and line current distortions harm the unity power factor and efficiency. This article adopts a simple single-stage AC-DC converter with a high-power factor and low total harmonic distortion. The PI hysteresis current control was utilized to reduce the total harmonic distortion and increase the power factor at full load. The PI controller was added to the outer voltage loop to regulate the output voltage. Ziegler-Nichol's tuning method was used to determine the controller gain levels. Simulation results were obtained for the AC-DC converter at a constant switching frequency to show the benefits of the proposed control method, which has a low total harmonic distortion and a high-power factor compared with cases without a controller. The proposed control method is accurate and efficient for achieving the power factor correction converter. Besides, the proposed control was stable during dynamic and steady-state responses.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Single-phase diode rectifiers are used in industrial applications, where the AC line input voltage is rectified and filtered using large electrolytic capacitors. This process, which includes nonlinear and storage components, generates harmonics and line current distortions. Total harmonic distortion (THD) is the term for these defects that harm the unity power factor (UPF) and efficiency. Power factor correction (PFC) and efficiency have taken on greater significance for power converters, and PFC converters are typically used to address line current harmonic issues with rectifiers [1]. Power factor (PF) is the cosine of the phase angle between the current and voltage waveforms for pure sine waves. It is required for AC-DC converters to meet international standards like IEC 61000-3-2 and IEEE-519. PFC can lower harmonics in the line current, improve power system capacity and efficiency, and lower user utility expenditures. Desirable PFC technique characteristics can be split into two categories: features on the input side include sinusoidal input current with nearly one-to-one PF functioning, reduced EMI filters, and insensitivity to minor signal disturbances in the load. In contrast, the output characteristics include good line and load control, minimal output voltage ripple, quick output dynamics (i.e., high bandwidth), and numerous output voltage levels if required by the application [2], [3]. Passive and active PFC are the two major approaches to power factor correction.

Passive PFC uses the inductive filter method, which requires an inductor to be placed between the rectifier output and the capacitor. Choosing the inductance value depends on the operation mode. The

resonance input filter method uses a series filter, which can achieve a high PF of 0.94. Passive PFC has drawbacks, including a large reactive element size, high THD, a lower PF compared to active schemes, and a lack of cost-effectiveness [2].

Active PFC techniques can be classified into buck, boost, buck-boost, SEPIC, and cuk converter [4]–[10]. These converters provide simple configurations for various input and output voltage conversion ratios. In contrast, control methods can be classified according to the input current control method, such as average current, peak current, and hysteresis current control (HCC) [11]–[13]. Some techniques can be used to perform the voltage or current control, such as sliding, predictive, passivity, and fuzzy logic control [14]–[18]. Active PFC techniques have the following advantages: lower harmonic content in the input current compared to the passive methods, a reduced root mean square (RMS) current rating of the output filter capacitor, and a UPF equal to 0.99 with a THD of 3% to 5%. Finally, active PFC techniques will outperform passive PFC techniques in size, weight, and cost for higher power levels. Many topologies are used to achieve PFC, as shown in Figure 1. The non-isolated type is also used in low and medium-power applications. There are differences in the operating modes and control methods used for each converter, including modes such as continuous conduction mode (CCM), discontinuous conduction mode (DCM), and boundary conduction mode (BCM). The DC-DC circuit converter changes a DC voltage difference to a higher or lower level. The voltage regulator is commonly used in switch-mode power supply (SMPS) applications. In this paper, section 2 introduces the boost topology design and operation. Section 3 presents the proposed system using PI-HCC of the boost PFC converter. Section 4 presents the simulation results and discussions for the proposed method. Finally, the conclusions for this paper are given in section 5.

Figure 1. Power converter topologies: (a) non isolated power topology and (b) isolated power topology

2. DESIGN AND OPERATION OF THE BOOST CONVERTER

While the switch is on, as shown in Figure 2, it represents a short circuit and should provide zero resistance to the current flow. As a result, the entire current will flow through the switch and back to the AC input source when the switch is on. It is assumed that the switch is turned on for a time T_{on} and turned off for a time T_{off} . The inductor's polarity is switched around in this mode, as shown in Figure 3. The polarity switching keeps the current flowing in the same direction through the load and steps up the output voltage because the inductor, in this case, serves as a source in addition to the input source. The energy stored in the inductor is released and dissipated in the load resistance [19]. The boost converter's transfer function, the duty cycle (D), and the LC filter are determined as follows [20]:

$$\frac{V_o}{V_{in}} = \frac{T_s}{T_{off}} = \frac{1}{1-D} \quad (1)$$

where V_{in} is the input voltage, V_o is the desired output voltage, and T_s is the time switching. D is determined by (2):

$$D = 1 - \frac{V_{in} * \eta}{V_o} \quad (2)$$

η is the boost converter's efficiency, estimated to be 80%. The inductor's value can be calculated by (3),

$$L = \frac{V_{in} * (V_o - V_{in})}{\Delta I_l * F_s * V_o} \quad (3)$$

where ΔI_l is the inductor's ripple current, and F_s is the lowest switching frequency. Since the inductor is unknown, it is impossible to determine the ripple current, hence, 20% to 40% of the output current (I_o) is a fair range to use as a good approximation for the inductor ripple current in (4),

$$\Delta I_l = (0.2 \text{ to } 0.4) * I_{o(max)} * \frac{V_o}{V_{in}} \quad (4)$$

where $I_{o(max)}$ is the maximum output current necessary in the application, and the output's capacitor $C_{o(min)}$, which is selected according in (5):

$$C_{o(min)} = \frac{I_{o(max)} * D}{F_s * \Delta V_o} \tag{5}$$

where ΔV_o is the desired output voltage ripple, the equivalent series resistance of the used output's capacitor (*ESR*) causes more ripples in the output voltage, as given in (6):

$$\Delta V_{o(ESR)} = ESR \left(\frac{I_{o(max)}}{1-D} + \frac{\Delta I_l}{2} \right) \tag{6}$$

where $\Delta V_{o(ESR)}$ is the additional output voltage ripple due to the capacitor's *ESR*.

Figure 2. ON-switch boost converter

Figure 3. OFF- switch boost converter

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This work aims to measure PF and THD values in the case of a resistive load, which was used with the boost converter. The applied input was a single-phase source with a frequency of 50 Hz. The AC input side was connected to a full-wave rectifier to convert the voltage from the AC form to the DC form for the designed voltage value. The prime purpose of the boost converter type is to raise the value of V_o to a higher value, which is determined based on D . The boost converter topology has remarkable advantages, such as its simple design and continuous current form at either the input or output sides.

The PI control was adopted in this work to reduce THD and improve PF. K_p and K_i gains of the controller were adjusted using Ziegler Nichol's tuning method to achieve PFC. Figure 4 illustrates the proposed PI hysteresis current control Simulink model. In contrast, the output is connected to a PI controller to obtain an accurate value for V_o , low THD, and a high PF. The inductor current I_l can be obtained depending on the sensed V_{in} and V_o , as shown in Figure 4. The boost converter has two distinct states: The T_{on} , in which the switch is closed, and the T_{off} , in which the switch is made open. The estimated $I_l(t)$ can be expressed as in (7) and (8).

$$L \frac{dI_l}{dt} = V_{in}(t) \tag{7}$$

$$L \frac{dI_l}{dt} = V_{in} - V_o \tag{8}$$

Since the $I_l(t)$ can be obtained by integrating the two states. The boost inductor current is continuously compared with the reference current waveform obtained from the voltage control loop, and the error signal after amplification is fed to the hysteresis comparator. When the actual inductor current goes above the reference current, the comparator changes its state to switch off the boost switch and the current ramp goes down. When the actual current falls below the reference current, it changes states again and turns the boost switch on. Figure 5 depicts the current control scheme's general hysteresis for 5(a) functional diagram and 5(b) current and PWM waveforms. The basic equations of reference current (I_{ref}) and controller output (U) for the PI-HCC method are given in (9) and (10) [1],

$$I_{ref} = \frac{(V_{ref} - V_o)(K_p + \frac{K_i}{s})I_l}{V_{rms}^2} \tag{9}$$

$$U = (I_{ref} - I_l)(K_p + \frac{K_i}{s}) \tag{10}$$

where V_{ref} is the reference voltage, and V_{rms} is the input voltage root mean square.

Figure 4. PI-HCC Simulink model for PFC boost converter

Figure 5. HCC scheme (a) functional diagram and (b) current and PWM waveforms

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation is done using MATLAB/Simulink for a single-phase AC-DC converter. The PI-controlled compensator drives the outer loop, and the current-controlled PI controller powers the inner current loop. The entire system is simulated while considering the specifications listed in Table 1. The average current control published in [21] was re-simulated to confirm the simulation methodology validity adopted in this study. It was noticed that both the re-simulation results and the published results were identical. The relevant curves of the re-simulation results are inserted in the supplementary materials.

Table 1. Specification and components used in the simulation of AC-DC boost converter

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Input voltage	V_{in}	40	V(RMS)
Supply frequency	F	50	Hz
Output voltage	V_o	100	V
Load	R	100	Ω
Capacitor	C_o	1000	μF
Inductor	L	3	mH
Output power	P_o	100	W
Switching frequency	F_s	21	kHz

Before applying the proposed control technique, the traditional system showed that PF was 0.9245, 0.9245, and 0.9983 for the R, RL, and RLC loads, respectively. Furthermore, the THD level was 63.85%, 63.87%, and 71.92% for the same loads. After applying the proposed control technique, R of 100 Ω was used as a 100% load for the simulation, as shown in Table 2. Figures 6(a)-(f) shows the simulated results since (a) I_{in} & V_{in} , (b) I_o & V_o , (c) I_R & V_R , (d) P_{in} & P_o , (e) THD %, and (f) PF. The simulation results show that the proposed system for the PFC boost converter with PI control for the resistive load is efficient. The PI control technique was used to regulate the output voltage at 100 V and achieve a sinusoidal form for the input current in the AC-DC boost converter. Hence, the PI control offers a limited THD, and the PF is close to the correct one. As a result, the system would be applicable in various industrial applications, whether the load is linear or non-linear. The simulation results of the PI control with the R load are listed in Table 2. Moreover, Table 3 compares the re-simulated results with the proposed system in this study.

Figure 6. Steady-state response for PFC boost converter (a) I_{in} & V_{in} , (b) I_o & V_o , (c) I_R & V_R , (d) P_{in} & P_o , (e) THD %, and (f) PF

Table 2. Simulation results for the boost converter PI-HCC with R load

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit	Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Peak input voltage	V_{in}	56.56	V	Input power	P_{in}	110	W
Supply frequency	F	50	Hz	Output power	P_o	100	W
Output voltage	V_o	100	V	Rectifier current	I_R	3.9	A
Load	R	100	Ω	Rectifier voltage	V_R	54.92	V
Input current	I_{in}	4	A	Power factor	PF	0.9999	-
Output current	I_o	1	A	Total harmonic distortion	THD	2.61	%

This study aims to achieve a high PF and a low THD, which increases the efficiency of the boost converter for different applications, such as switching mode power supplies and LED gate drive circuits. This goal was efficiently achieved using an uncomplicated proposed design. In contrast, some complex designs and control methods were presented in [6], which recently introduced a literature review for the boost converter topology, such as the traditional bridge boost converter with PFC, PFC with pseudo-continuous conduction, interleaved PFC, hybrid interleaved PFC, and PFC with a bidirectional switch. However, detailed the emerging disadvantages of such topologies, which include difficulty in implementing control, high cost, and the complexity of the design with high distortions for the used topologies with the boost converter, affecting the efficiency and performance of the converter in various power applications [6], [22]–[24]. Moreover, the proposed design was modified to improve the performance since PF and THD showed 0.9999 and 2.61%, respectively, which is better than those who adopted the same topology as our work in [21], [25]. The adopted average current control method in [21] has some demerits, such as the following: the inductor’s current must be sensed, which is a difficult task, and the current mode control system requires the use of the current error amplifier. Besides, a compensation network must be constructed that considers the variable operating points of the converter that uses the error amplifier. Published results of [21] indicated 3.49% and 0.99972 of the THD and the PF, respectively.

Table 3. Comparison results between re-simulated results and the proposed for boost converter R load

Refs	Control Technique	Topology	Input voltage (V)	Output Voltage (V)	Supply frequency (Hz)	Load (Ω)	Input current (A)	Output current (A)	THD (%)	P. F
[21]	PI average current control	Boost	56.56*	100*	50*	100*	4.2*	1.02*	6.81*	0.9997*
This work	PI hysteresis current control	Boost	56.56	100	50	100	4	1	2.61	0.9999

*Re-simulated result

In contrast, the adopted HCC has the following advantages: a compensating ramp is unnecessary, and the input current waveforms have little distortion. A comparison is introduced here between the most

important results obtained from this work and the published results in the literature. This comparison is presented in Table 4 for the R load. The current work aims to achieve a high PFC with the lowest harmonic ratio through a simple and easy control technique with high efficiency. This objective was achieved using the Simulink platform of MATLAB.

Table 4. Comparison results between refs [21], [25], and the proposed for boost converter R load

Refs	Control Technique	Topology	THD (%)	P. F	V_o (V)
[21]	PI average current control	Boost	*6.81 +3.49	0.9997 0.99	100 100
[25]	Peak current control	Boost	3.08	0.99	400
	Hysteresis current control	Boost	4.28	0.99	400
This work	PI hysteresis current control	Boost	2.61	0.9999	100

*Re-simulated result, †Published result

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has proposed a single-stage AC–DC converter with a high PF and low THD. Besides, the proposed converter's analysis, design, and simulation results have also been presented. The proposed converter is a PFC boost converter with PI-HCC. The proposed converter has a simple design and a reasonable price for practical use. As a result of this, the suggested converter is appropriate for various power applications. By utilizing the proposed control for the PFC boost converter, the proposed converter has a high PF of 0.9999 and low THD to comply with IEC 61000-3-2 harmonic regulation. The PFC buck and buck-boost type AC-DC converters can be operated in CCM using the PI-HCC. The proposed converter offers a low THD of 2.61% at full load thanks to the single-stage converter. In the future, it is planned to investigate this system experimentally since the proposed system was successfully achieved in the research thanks to the Simulink platform of MATLAB.

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